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Annotation: *In this article, the quality parameters of fabrics made from a blend of 50% cotton and 50% modal fibers, 100% cotton fibers, and 50% cotton and 50% polyester fibers were determined and analyzed.*

Key words: *wrinkle resistance, non-pilling, low shrinkage and increased capacity, dimensional stability, plain-dyed and multi-colored suit fabrics*

1. INTRODUCTION

The textile industry of Uzbekistan has centuries-old traditions of processing local raw materials: cotton fiber - the national wealth of the country, silk, wool and leather. The Great Silk Road passed through Uzbekistan and cotton and silk fabrics, elegant and casual clothes, national footwear, suzani with original designs produced by Uzbek artisans were known in many countries of the world.

In the modern world, the textile industry has a high rating among industries engaged in export. It has the widest range of exported goods - from yarn to finished products (garments and knitwear). From this point of view, the export potential of the industry is quite large-scale, and the directions of its development can be selected from the conditions at the time of decision-making: the presence of a strategic investor, the global commodity market situation, the effectiveness of the existing business plan, the level of personnel training in accordance with the requirements of export production, etc.

Suit fabrics are used to make men's, women's and children's products, various seasonal clothing, jackets, blazers, trousers, skirts, etc. According to their purpose, suit products are divided into elegant, casual, sports, corporate and special. Depending on the purpose of the product, suit fabrics are subject to aesthetic, hygienic, technological, economic requirements, as well as wear resistance requirements. With the development of the textile industry, the range of suit fabrics is also changing. Analysis of suit fabrics showed that the small width of the fabric and their structure do not meet modern consumer requirements.

The most important properties of suit fabrics are their wrinkle resistance, non-pilling, low shrinkage and increased ability to retain the shape given to the products. To reduce wrinkle resistance and shrinkage, it is recommended to treat suit fabrics with low-wrinkle and low-shrink finishes. The properties of suit fabrics are improved by introducing polyester and polyamide fibers into the mixture with subsequent stabilization of the fabrics, thereby increasing resistance to abrasion.

Among the wide range of suit fabrics produced by the textile industry, fabrics made of natural fibers occupy a special place. Recently, suit fabrics have been produced from a mixture of cotton with chemical fibers, such as viscose, lavsan, and nitron. The range of cotton fabrics produced annually changes by 10-12% due to fabrics of new structures and finishes.

Since suit fabrics fit the human body, they must meet hygienic requirements that take into account the season, climatic conditions, and age of the person.

Taking into account the healing properties of natural fibers and their positive effect on human health gives good results in the development and production of a new range of suit fabrics.

A special place is occupied by the production of suit fabrics for men's, women's, and children's casual and formal wear. For this, their properties must meet a number of requirements. Fabrics must meet a number of consumer requirements, namely, during consumption they must meet the requirements of shape stability, seasonality, age category, weaving design, hygienic properties, appearance, fashion.

2.METHODS

When developing new ranges of suit fabrics at textile enterprises, special attention is paid to the fibrous composition of raw materials, properties and compatibility of components.

In the conditions of a market economy at textile industry enterprises, samples were selected from the manufactured suit fabrics obtained from local raw materials with different fibrous compositions for conducting experiments to determine the physical and mechanical properties.

The test results are presented in Table 1.

Таблица 1

Влияние волокнистого состава на физико-механические свойства костюмных тканей

Т/р	Fibrous composition	Breaking load, Н		Breaking elongation, mm		Thickness, mm
		По основе	По утку	По основе	По утку	
1.	Made from a blend of 50% cotton and 50% modal fiber	463,6	460,8	27,2	52,6	1,7
2.	100% cotton fiber	305,5	262,5	20,3	25,2	1,6
3.	Made from a blend of 50% cotton and 50% polyester fiber	531,6	567,7	34,0	31,8	1,65

Based on the test results given in Table 1, graphs of changes in breaking load and breaking elongation for the warp and weft, thickness of suit fabrics made from a blend of fibers were constructed.

1- main;
2- weft.

2-fig. Change in breaking elongation of suit fabric.

3-fig. Changing the thickness of suit fabric.

3. RESULTS

Suiting fabrics include dense, wear-resistant, durable fabrics. Most of them are plain-dyed and variegated suiting fabrics, which are made mainly from carded single yarn with a linear density of 25-70 tex or twisted yarn with a linear density of 15.4 tex x 2-25 tex x 2. Recently, suiting fabrics with the addition of chemical fibers have been produced.

During the finishing process, fabrics are processed to make them wrinkle-resistant and shrink-resistant. The group of suiting fabrics is divided into the following subgroups: plain-dyed, special, variegated, melange. Comparison of the obtained test results with the indicators of suiting fabric from a blend of 50% cotton and 50% modal fibers shows that the breaking load of the warp of suiting fabric from 100% cotton decreased by 34.1%, by the weft by 43.1%, breaking elongation of the warp by 25.4%, by the weft by 52.0%, and for suiting fabric from a blend of 50% cotton and 50% polyester fiber, the breaking load of the warp increased by 12.7%, by the weft by 18.9%, breaking elongation of the warp by 20.5%, and by the weft decreased by 39.5%. As can be seen from the research results, the indicators of the physical and mechanical properties of suiting fabric from a blend of 40% wool + 60% polyester fiber are higher compared to the indicators of other suiting fabrics.

4. CONCLUSION

As a result of the conducted research it was established that the suit fabric made from a mixture of 50% cotton and 50% modal fiber has higher warp and weft breaking load and warp and weft breaking elongation compared to the suit fabrics made from a mixture of 50% wool + 50% viscose and 100% cotton.

REFERENCES:

1. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан Шавката Мирзиёева “О Программе мер по дальнейшему развитию текстильной и швейно-трикотажной промышленности на 2017-2019 годы” от 21 декабря 2016 года открыло новые возможности для совершенствования отрасли.
2. Караева Т.Ю. «Оптимизация параметров заправки и выработки тканей с поперечными и продольными полосами на бесчелночных ткацких станках» Автореф. дис. ... канд. техн. наук.- Кострома: Косоткзти, 1992.
3. Abdullaev U.T. Research on the technology of production of new composite fabrics based on complex weaves. Candidate. dissertation. Abstract of the work - Т.: TITLP, 2007.
4. Дамянов Д. и другие. Строение ткани и современные методы ее проектирование.-М.: Легкая и пищевая промышленность, 1984.-236 б
5. Литовченко А.Г. Разработка метода проектирования и оптимальных параметров изготовления ткани из комбинированных нитей. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата технических наук. Москва. МГТА- 1995г.
6. Лусгартен Н. В. Разработка методов оптимизации и стабилизации технологического режима процесса образования ткани: Автореф. дис. ... докт. техн. наук.– Кострома: КТИ, 1983.-32 с.
7. Atanafasov Muhiddin Rakhmonovich “Changes in the quality indicators of yarns” //Innovative Development in Educational Activities // ISSN: 2181-3523 Volume 2, Issue 4,2023.
8. Atanafasov Muhiddin Rakhmonovich, Ochilov To‘lqin Ashurovich, Rahimjonov Husanboy Rahimjonov “Changes in the unevenness indicators of wicks obtained from mixtures of different compositions and processed fibers” //Innovative Development in Educational Activities // Volume 2, Issue 4, ISSN: 2181-3523, 2023.
9. Atanafasov M.R., Ochilov T.A., Usmonova Sh.A., Yuldashyev J.N., Hakimov Sh.H. Influence of Cotton Fiber of Different Composition and Secondary Material Resources on Single-Cycle Elongation Deformation of Yarns // International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology – India, Volume 11, Issue 2, February 2022. pp.1135-1137.